

How to improve the conservation of species-rich grasslands with result-oriented payment schemes?

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ABSTRACT

Specific mechanisms for result-oriented payment schemes using vascular plant taxa have been discussed as possible targeted approaches for promoting European species-rich grasslands. Most indicator lists are restricted to a limited number of frequently occurring indicator taxa. However, these lists often do not adequately reflect the most valuable grasslands in terms of conservation. Thus, we developed a procedure for selecting indicator species from an expanded checklist as well as a procedure for weighting indicator species based on their indicator power in terms of conservation criteria. The case study region was the federal state of Brandenburg (Germany). The database contained Brandenburg's vegetation mapping data and a simple indicator checklist from a previous agri-environmental program. For the conservation quality criteria, we used species number, number of extensive grassland species, number of threatened red list species and indices combining two of these criteria. The new expanded checklist resulted in 71 indicator taxa. We recommended a weighting factor that considers the indicator power of the index that combines extensively used species and red list species. Regression analyses were conducted to test the improvements resulting from each step of the approach. The determination coefficient of the regression between the number of indicator taxa and the quality index increased in the following order: simple checklist, expanded checklist and expanded weighted checklist (0.420, 0.654 and 0.782). The new, more differentiated list allows a 5-step payment approach. Generally, this procedure could be used to compile weighted indicator lists for other regions.

1. Introduction

Nature conservation payment schemes or payments for ecosystem services, including agri-environmental schemes (AES), are discussed as one important approach for nature conservation in Europe (Batory, Dicks, Kleijn, & Sutherland, 2015) and worldwide (Schomers & Matzdorf, 2013). However, there are serious concerns regarding the effectiveness of these kind of payment instruments (Sutcliffe et al., 2015). Most of the payment approaches are action-based (or measure-oriented). Land stewards are paid for a specific action/change in land use. Result-oriented (also called result-based or performance-based) schemes are discussed as one approach for better targeting and improved effectiveness (Burton & Schwarz, 2013). Specifically, in Europe, there is an ongoing discussion to design AES within the Common

Agricultural policy that is more result-based (Fleury, Seres, Dobremez, Nettier, & Pauthenet, 2015; Herzon et al., 2018). One of the major challenges for AES in general and for result-based approaches specifically is the development of appropriate indicators to measure the success of the payment.

Species-rich grasslands are one of the habitats in most need of conservation in Europe (Habel et al., 2013). However, the ongoing intensification of land use over the last 50 years, including the conversion of grasslands into arable lands as well as the abandonment of extensively used grasslands, has caused further loss of this kind of high nature-value farmland in Europe (Auffret, Kimberley, Plue, & Walden, 2018; Baldock, 1990; Bignal & McCracken, 1996; Dahlström, Lennartsson, Wissman, & Frycklund, 2008; Hünig & Benzler, 2017). This scenario becomes increasingly remarkable as AES takes place on

Abbreviations: AES, agri-environmental schemes; HNV, high nature value; BBK, Brandenburg's habitat mapping; SP, number of species; EXT, number of species indicating extensive use; RL1, number of Brandenburg's red list species of threatened vascular plants including species in the early-warning stage; RL2, similar to RL1 but excluding species in the early-warning stage; Xa, index combining EXT and RL1; Xb, index combining EXT and RL2; Xc, index combining SP and RL1; Xd, index combining SP and RL2; N, frequency of species occurrence; mF, mean indicator value for moisture; mR, mean indicator value for soil pH; SD, standard deviation; P, significance level; R², determination coefficient of regression analysis

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much of the grasslands in Europe. In 2013, the amount of agricultural areas under agri-environmental systems in the EU was 47 million ha, representing 26% of the agricultural area in the EU (Eurostat, 2017). However, current agri-environmental measures are not sufficiently focused on species-rich grasslands (Kaligarič, Čuš, Škornik, & Ivajnšič, 2019).

For several years, due to development, result-oriented payment schemes have been introduced for grasslands, specifically in some European countries (Burton & Schwarz, 2013; Herzon et al., 2018). For most of these payment schemes, vascular plants are used as indicators. Vascular plants are an easily recognizable part of biodiversity in grasslands. Although this group of organisms is not a surrogate for all biodiversity in the grasslands (Blanckenhorn, Jochmann, & Walter, 2018), correlations of plant richness to the richness of other organisms such as wild pollinators, grasshoppers and gastropods could be verified (Brunbjerg et al., 2018; Ebeling, Klein, Schumacher, Weisser, & Tschardtke, 2008; Koch et al., 2013; Papanikolaou et al., 2017; Walter, Grünig, Schüpbach, & Schmid, 2007). For better practical implementation, a checklist of easily identifiable plant taxa (single species and species groups) that indicates plant species richness serves as the basis for incentive payments to farmers (e.g., Briemle & Oppermann, 2003; Matzdorf, Kaiser, & Rohner, 2008; Wittig, Kemmermann, & Zacharias, 2006). According to this approach, the number of identified indicator taxa on transect segments must equal or exceed a threshold value to be eligible for payment. Four indicator plant taxa per test area are the common threshold value for being considered an eligible grassland in Germany. Most of the indicator checklists are designed for extensively managed grasslands, which in the past were predominantly intensively cultivated (e.g., Kaiser, Rohner, Matzdorf, & Kiesel, 2010). These grasslands mainly have moderate levels of species richness. The checklists used in the abovementioned programs are mostly restricted to a limited number of more frequently occurring indicator taxa.

In some programs, efforts to establish a multistage concept of payments considering various conservation quality levels for grasslands have been implemented. An example of these efforts is the AES of the state Saxony (Germany) and the farmland indicator for high nature value (HNV) areas in Germany, which incorporated a tiered payment with threshold values of 4, 6 and 8 plant indicator taxa (Anonymous, 2013; Anonymous, 2017; Goldberg, 2013). However, even though the multilevel approach was used, there was a need to improve the identification of highest HNV grasslands by indicator methods, especially for the semi-natural areas of grasslands that serve the most important grassland habitat for rare species (for HNV grasslands, see Anonymous (2017)). We argue that expanding to a multistage concept with several threshold values requires an enhanced indicator list that encompasses indicator species for grasslands with moderate to higher conservation quality levels. A further important issue is that the common indicator approach neglects the different indicator powers of indicator species. Goldberg (2013) demonstrated that taxa with close affinities to particularly species-rich plant communities occurred more frequently in grassland habitats of the highest HNV. This finding supports the assumption that the introduction of weighting factors for indicator taxa could lead to a more accurate classification of grasslands into conservation quality categories.

The objective of our research was to develop an improved indicator-based approach for result-oriented payment systems, taking into account the weaknesses of existing approaches. Using a case study region in Germany as an example, we develop (i) a procedure for selecting indicator species for an expanded checklist and (ii) a procedure for weighting indicator species.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Database and study area

The starting point of the method development was the checklist of

27 plant taxa for species-rich grassland that was compiled for a former agri-environmental program in the federal state of Brandenburg (Germany) (Kaiser et al., 2010). The taxa in this list were organized into single species. The choice of new indicator species and the determination of species weighting factors were carried out on the basis of Brandenburg's habitat mapping data (BBK data, see <https://ifu.brandenburg.de/cms/detail.php/bb1.c.315445.de>, release April 2017). The database consists of vegetation surveys mapped according to the habitat code of the Federal State of Brandenburg (Anonymous, 2004). The BBK database contains both area-wide biotope mapping (areas subjected to the Flora-Fauna-Habitat Directive as well as large-scale reserves) and selective biotope mapping of landscape components of particular relevance to nature conservation. A biotope in the sense of this biotope mapping is a clearly distinguishable area in the terrain, which is characterised by a relatively uniform vegetation and/or utilisation structure (LGB undated). We used vegetation surveys of mapping units of grasslands (presence/absence data of species). Only vegetation surveys with a minimum species number of five were involved to exclude artifacts. The data included 30310 vegetation surveys of grassland areas and were collected from 1992 to 2015 by botanists on behalf of the Brandenburg State Office for the Environment. Multiple vegetation surveys of the same area were not included in the data set. The areas of the individual mapping units varied but were mostly far greater than the minimum area specified by Mueller-Dombois and Ellenberg (1974) for vegetation surveys in grassland habitats (only 5 mapping units were smaller than 100 m²). Fig. 1 depicts the spatial allocation of the included grasslands.

2.2. Assessment criteria for species richness

As criteria for the assessment of conservation quality, we used the following variables: (i) the number of species (SP) and (ii) the number of species indicating extensive use (EXT). Two further criteria were derived from Brandenburg's red list of endangered vascular plants (Ristow et al., 2006). This red list covers the following categories: 0 - extinct, 1 - threatened with extinction, 2 - severely endangered, 3 - endangered, G - endangered without precise assignment to one of the categories, V - species in the early-warning stage (population in Brandenburg not yet endangered, but showing strong decline in the recent past), R - seldom without direct risk of extinction, and D - inadequate state of the available data for classification. Criterion (iii) includes the number of red list species found in categories 1, 2, 3, G, V, and R (RL1). Criterion (iv) is analogous to (iii) but excludes species that are in the early-warning stage (RL2). In the last criterion (iv), indices were formed (Xa to Xd). This type of variable always consisted of a combination of two criteria mentioned above. The calculation was conducted according to the following formulas:

$$Xa_i = 0.5 \times \left(\frac{EXT_i}{\text{mean}(EXT_{all})} + \frac{RL1_i}{\text{mean}(RL1_{all})} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$Xb_i = 0.5 \times \left(\frac{EXT_i}{\text{mean}(EXT_{all})} + \frac{RL2_i}{\text{mean}(RL2_{all})} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$Xc_i = 0.5 \times \left(\frac{SP_i}{\text{mean}(SP_{all})} + \frac{RL1_i}{\text{mean}(RL1_{all})} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$Xd_i = 0.5 \times \left(\frac{SP_i}{\text{mean}(SP_{all})} + \frac{RL2_i}{\text{mean}(RL2_{all})} \right) \quad (4)$$

where i = single plot, and all = all plots of the database.

The formulas were derived from the quotient index method used in plant breeding to integrate several traits of different scales into one selection index (Ruebenbauer & Wegrzyn, 1963).

To be considered a group of species indicating extensive use (EXT species), the following conditions had to be met: not ubiquitously occurring, not nonnative to grasslands, typically occurring in extensively

Fig. 1. Left: Location of the federal state of Brandenburg in Germany. Right: Allocation of the selected grassland plots from the BBK database in a point display (N = 30310).

used grasslands, not highly tolerant to frequent mowing and heavy grazing, and not occurring in nitrogen-rich sites (as high nitrogen levels negatively affect species diversity (Payne et al., 2017)). The classification of species into this group was based on the indicator values for nitrogen (Ellenberg & Leuschner, 2010) as well as on information from floristic literature (Jäger & Werner, 2005) and from the floristic database Biolflor (Klotz, Kühn, & Durka, 2002), in particular the indicator values for the susceptibility to mowing according to Briemle, Nitsche, and Nitsche, (2002)). For species with a focus on different habitats, we have opted for a not too strict exclusion. A typical example is *Filipendula ulmaria*, a plant species with main occurrences in wet fallows and herbaceous corridors, but also in wet meadows with one cut a year. We also considered the occurrence of these species as an indication of extensive grassland use (in a broader sense). The appendix to this publication contains a list of species that we have classified as EXT species in the database used.

The quality criteria address different aspects of species diversity in grasslands. The strictness of the criteria in terms of conservation value increases from criterion (i) to criterion (iv). We used a range of criteria because it was not clear how the effect of a single step was correlated with different variants of species diversity.

2.3. Developing the expanded checklist of indicator species

First, we developed a preliminary list of indicator species among the EXT species in the BBK database. The existing checklist was supplemented by appropriate species, taking into account balanced indicator species proportions for the most important habitat types of extensively used grasslands in Brandenburg (wet grasslands generally including *Molinia*-meadows, periodically wet grasslands in flood plains, moderately moist grasslands lower in nutrients, sandy dry grasslands, and

calcareous dry grasslands). Then, we calculated the following parameters from each grassland plot of the BBK database: SP, EXT, RL1, RL2, indices Xa to Xd (see Formulas 1–4), and unweighted mean indicator values for moisture (mF) and soil pH (mR) according to Ellenberg & Leuschner, 2010. Using plots where a tested indicator species occurred, we calculated the following parameters for each potential indicator species: number of plots with occurrence (N); the averages of mF and mR as well as the standard deviation (SD) of mF and mR. In the first step we determined the site boundaries of each indicator species using the plots where the respective test indicator occurred. The boundaries were determined from $mF \pm SD$ and $mR \pm SD$. In the second step, we selected all plots that were within the identified boundaries (i.e., including also the plots in which the test species did not occur). This approach ensured that only the plots with the typical site conditions of an indicator species for moisture and soil pH were included in the significance testing. Next, the selected plots were divided into the following groups: plots with occurrence (i) and absence (ii) of the selected indicator species. Then, Mann-Whitney U-tests were conducted to find significant differences between the two groups regarding Xb. For Xb, we chose a selection criterion that, on one hand, reflects the species richness of extensively used grassland and, on the other hand, takes the aspect of species conservation into account. The subcomponent EXT appeared to be more suitable than SP for this purpose, as the latter may also contain numerous non-grassland species and ubiquitous. RL1 has a greater overlap with EXT because this variable also includes the wide group of grassland species in the early-warning stage. Therefore, we found the combination of EXT and the strictest of the quality criteria used, RL2, to be best for the significance testing of potential indicator species. For illustration, in Fig. 2, we show distributions of 3 selected species regarding Xb. Taking *Succisa pratensis* as an example, an Xb median of 5 means that in locations where this species

Fig. 2. Distribution differences (boxplots of data) in the presence and absence of a test species with regard to index Xb. All group differences inside a graphic box are significant at $P < 0.05$ (Mann-Whitney U test).

occurs, biodiversity in the form of a combined value from EXT and RL2 is, on average, 5 times higher than the average in the BBK database. The 3 species examples in Fig. 2 demonstrate how different the indicator power can be in terms of species richness. Test species whose occurrence did not result in a significant increase in Xb were excluded from the list. Species that looked similar to one another and thus were hard to distinguish were pooled together as a single species group. A group of species in one taxon on the checklist were counted only one time even though more than one species of the group occurred on a test plot. Very rare indicator species (occurring on < 100 plots in the BBK database) were removed from the list or were assigned to a group taxon, if appropriate.

2.4. Derivation of weighting factors for the indicator species

The quality criteria described above were the starting point of the weighting procedure.

The mean quality criterion of an indicator species was calculated, taking into account the plots containing the respective indicator species:

$$\text{mean}(QC_i) = \frac{\sum QC_j}{\sum N} \quad (5)$$

where $\text{mean}(QC_i)$ = mean quality criterion of indicator species i , QC_j = quality criterion of plot j containing indicator species i , and N = number of plots containing indicator species i .

For the group taxa, we calculated a mean quality criterion of the group, considering the frequency of occurrence of the species:

$$\text{mean}(QC_{GR}) = \frac{\sum (N_i \times \text{mean}(QC_i))}{\sum N_i} \quad (6)$$

where $\text{mean}(QC_{GR})$ = mean quality criterion of the indicator group, $\text{mean}(QC_i)$ = mean quality criterion of the group indicator species i , and N_i = respective number of plots containing group indicator species i .

To develop a general method for the derivation of the weighting factors, we needed an external starting reference value that could not come from a randomly selected database. The total floristic species number of extensive two-cut systems or extensively and continuously grazed systems (0.5–1.5 livestock units, 1 livestock unit = 500 kg live weight) was specified as 30–50 (Taube, Benke, Elsässer, Ernst, & Pickert, 2002). Considering this information, we set a species number of 30 as a reference point for the determination of species-rich grasslands. The corresponding reference values for the criteria EXT, RL1 and RL2 were derived by regression analysis using the BBK-database. First, we

Table 1

Correlation matrix of quality criteria (Pearson's correlation coefficients all significant at $P < 0.001$).

	EXT	RL1	RL2
SP	0.801	0.654	0.538
EXT		0.824	0.718
RL1			0.897

performed a correlation analysis to gain an overview about the pairwise relationships between the quality criteria. The correlation matrix in Table 1 demonstrates that it is advisable to apply a stepwise regression approach for determining the reference basis of the other quality criteria by using the data pairs SP/EXT, EXT/RL1 and RL1/RL2. As a result, SP = 30 was related to EXT = 11.5, RL1 = 4 and RL2 = 2.

Based on the abovementioned quality criteria, we generated different sets of weighting factors for all indicator taxa of the new expanded checklist. To generate these weighting factors, we divided each mean quality criterion of an indicator taxon by the reference value of this criterion. The value of the weighting factors was the following: weighting factors < 1 were below the reference level, and those > 1 were above the reference level. In this paper, we refer to high-quality (with a high weighting factor) and low-quality (with a low weighting factor) indicator species as 'hard' and 'soft' indicator species, respectively. For composite criteria (indices), the weighting factors were calculated by averaging the weighting factors of the single components. Finally, we classified the weighting factors into factor levels with a fixed step range of 0.25 to allow easier use of the list in practice. Using the weighted indicator method, the number of indicator taxa per sample area resulted from the sum of the respective weighting factors of the indicator taxa occurring in the area. The effectiveness of the different weighting methods in predicting quality levels was tested by regression analysis.

2.5. Test of thresholds for incentive payments

Separately for the different indicator methods, we determined the changed number of plots that remain if the indicator threshold gradually increases. From this approach, we suggested thresholds of indicator numbers for the new expanded checklist and determined mean values and SDs within the classes with respect to the most suitable quality criterion.

All the described statistical analyses were carried out using the computer program IBM SPSS Statistics 22 (IBM, 2013).

Table 2
Indicator list with information on the range of moisture levels and weighting factors (the taxa from the old list are marked with an asterisk).

		Moisture level		Weighting factors based on:						
		SP	EXT	RL1	RL2	Xa	Xb	Xc	Xd	
< 4.8	moderately dry to dry									
4.8 – 5.6	moderately moist with trend towards dry									
5.7 – 6.5	moderately moist with trend towards wet									
> 6.5	wet									
■	occurrence within a moisture level									

No	Indicator species	Moisture level		Weighting factors based on:									
		SP	EXT	RL1	RL2	Xa	Xb	Xc	Xd				
1	<i>Achillea ptarmica</i> */ <i>salicifolia</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
2	<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.50	1.50	1.75	1.50	1.75	1.25	1.50
3	<i>Ajuga reptans</i> / <i>genevensis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.50	2.00	2.00	1.75	1.75	1.50	1.50
4	<i>Allium</i> sp.	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.25	1.75	2.00	1.50	1.75	1.50	1.50
5	<i>Angelica sylvestris</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.25	1.00
6	<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.00	1.00
7	<i>Anthyllis vulneraria</i>	■	■	■	■	1.75	2.75	3.25	4.50	3.00	3.50	2.50	3.00
8	<i>Armeria elongata</i> *	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.75
9	<i>Artemisia campestris</i>	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.75
10	<i>Bistorta officinalis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00
11	<i>Briza media</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.25	3.00	4.00	2.75	3.00	2.25	2.75
12	<i>Bromus erectus</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.75	1.25	1.50	1.25	1.25
13	<i>Caltha palustris</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25
14	<i>Campanula</i> sp.* (<i>C. patula</i> , <i>C. rotundifolia</i>)	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
15	<i>Cardamine pratensis</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
16	<i>Carex</i> sp. (large)*	■	■	■	■	0.75	0.75	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.75
17	<i>Carex</i> sp. (middle-small)* without <i>C. hirta</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.25
18	<i>Centaurea</i> sp.*	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25

No	Indicator species	Moisture level		Weighting factors based on:									
		SP	EXT	RL1	RL2	Xa	Xb	Xc	Xd				
19	<i>Cirsium oleraceum</i> *	■	■	■	■	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.50	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
20	<i>Cnidium dubium</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
21	<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.75	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
22	<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.00	1.00
23	<i>Daucus carota</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
24	<i>Dianthus</i> sp./ <i>Petrorhagia prolifera</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	2.50	1.50	1.75	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.50
25	<i>Erigeron acris</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	1.75	1.75
26	<i>Euphrasia</i> sp.	■	■	■	■	1.50	2.25	2.50	3.50	2.50	2.75	2.00	2.50
27	<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
28	<i>Filipendula vulgaris</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	3.00	4.25	2.50	3.25	2.25	2.75
29	<i>Fragaria viridis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	2.50	3.50	2.25	2.75	2.00	2.25
30	<i>Galium</i> sp.* (<i>G. album</i> , <i>G. palustre</i> , <i>G. uliginosum</i> , <i>G. verum</i>)	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
31	<i>Geranium</i> sp. – large-flowered (<i>G. palustre</i> , <i>G. pratense</i>)	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
32	<i>Geum rivale</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.75	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.25
33	<i>Helichrysum arenarium</i>	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
34	<i>Helictotrichon pubescens</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.75	2.00	2.25	1.75	2.00	1.50	1.75
35	<i>Hieracium pilosella</i> *	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.50	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
36	<i>Inula britannica</i> /l. <i>salicina</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.75	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.50
37	<i>Juncus</i> sp. (without <i>J. effusus</i>)	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00
38	<i>Knautia arvensis</i> */ <i>Scabiosa</i> sp.	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.50	1.50	1.75	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.50
39	<i>Lathyrus palustris</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.75	1.75	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25
40	<i>Lathyrus pratensis</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
41	<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
42	<i>Linum catharticum</i>	■	■	■	■	1.50	2.25	3.25	4.50	2.75	3.50	2.50	3.00
43	<i>Lotus</i> sp.*	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
44	<i>Luzula campestris</i> */ <i>L. multiflora</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25
45	<i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i>	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75
46	<i>Lythrum salicaria</i> *	■	■	■	■	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
47	<i>Orchids</i> (meadow orchids)	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	3.00	3.50	2.50	2.75	2.25	2.50

No	Indicator species	Moisture level		Weighting factors based on:									
		SP	EXT	RL1	RL2	Xa	Xb	Xc	Xd				
48	<i>Peucedanum oreoselinum</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.75	2.00	2.25	1.75	2.00	1.50	1.75
49	<i>Phleum phleoides</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	2.50	3.50	2.25	2.75	2.00	2.25
50	<i>Polygala</i> sp.	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	2.50	3.50	2.25	2.75	2.00	2.50
51	<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.50	2.00	1.50	1.75	1.50	1.50	1.25
52	<i>Potentilla palustris</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.50	2.25	2.50	1.75	2.00	1.50	1.75
53	<i>Primula veris</i> ssp. <i>veris</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.50	2.00	2.75	1.75	2.00	1.50	2.00
54	<i>Ranunculus acris</i> */ <i>R. auricomus</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.75
55	<i>Rhinanthus</i> sp.	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.75	2.25	2.50	2.00	2.00	1.75	1.75
56	<i>Salvia pratensis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	2.50	4.00	2.50	3.00	2.00	2.75
57	<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.50	2.00	1.25	1.50	1.25	1.50
58	<i>Saxifraga granulata</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.25	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.25
59	<i>Serratula tinctoria</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.75	2.75	3.00	2.25	2.50	2.00	2.25
60	<i>Silene flos-cuculi</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
61	<i>Stellaria graminea</i> */ <i>S. palustris</i> */ <i>Cerastium arvense</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
62	<i>Succisa pratensis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	3.00	3.50	2.50	2.75	2.25	2.50
63	<i>Thalictrum flavum</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.50	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.25	1.00
64	<i>Thymus pulegioides</i> /l. <i>serpyllum</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.75	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.00	1.50	1.75
65	<i>Tragopogon dubius</i> */ <i>T. pratensis</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
66	<i>Trifolium pratense</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
67	<i>Valeriana dioica</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	1.75	2.75	3.25	2.25	2.50	2.00	2.25
68	<i>Valeriana officinalis</i>	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.25	1.75	1.50	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.25
69	<i>Veronica chamaedrys</i> *	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	0.75	0.75	1.00	0.75	1.00	0.75
70	<i>Veronica spicata</i>	■	■	■	■	1.25	2.00	2.50	3.50	2.25	2.75	2.00	2.50
71	<i>Viola</i> sp. (without <i>V. arvensis</i>)	■	■	■	■	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00

Legend: Notes on the moisture levels (mean indicator values based on [Ellenberg & Leuschner, 2010](#)).

3. Results

3.1. Checklist and weighting factors

The indicator species that passed the test conditions are presented in Table 2. The expanded list represents a wide spectrum of moisture levels and contains common as well as rarer species. The weighting factors reflect a differentiated indication power of the species in terms of the respective quality criterion. The degree of differentiation was lowest for the indication of SP, and the degree increased in the order of SP to EXT to RL1 to RL2. The relationships between the number of indicator species on the one hand (calculated by the different weighting methods) and the quality criteria on the other hand were estimated by regression analysis. The effect of the different methods was assessed based on the determination coefficients from the regression analyses (Table 3A and B). In the case of the unweighted calculation, the comparison between the old and new lists showed that an increased number of indicator species from a list resulted in a better prediction of species richness, as expected. The relation of indicator species number to the developed indices specifically supported this finding. Table 3A demonstrates that the weighting methods using the old list resulted in only a minor improvement in predictability for most of the quality criteria. This result was expected because the proportion of 'hard' indicator species in the old list was low. However, in the case of the expanded list, the weighting method did not provide a benefit in terms of the prediction of species number. Here, the expansion of the indicator species list was the method of choice for improving the prediction. The stricter the quality criterion, the higher the increase in the determination coefficients comparing unweighted with weighted methods in Table 3B was. This result is an indication that the weighted calculation was primarily a means to improve the indicator method in terms of predicting rare and/or red list species.

If we only adjusted the weighting method to the strictest criteria RL2, then we would have neglected species richness as an important component of biodiversity in the landscape. Notably, when comparing

Table 3
Determination coefficients from regression analyses (relationship between number of weighted or unweighted indicator species and the quality data).

		Quality criterion per sample							
		SP R ² *	EXT R ² *	RL1 R ² *	RL2 R ² **	Xa R ² *	Xb R ² **	Xc R ² *	Xd R ² **
Number of indicator species per sample	unweighted	0.53	0.61	0.41	0.23	0.53	0.38	0.52	0.35
	weighted with SP	0.53	0.63	0.41	0.23	0.53	0.38	0.52	0.35
	weighted with EXT	0.54	0.64	0.43	0.26	0.56	0.41	0.54	0.37
	weighted with RL1	0.52	0.62	0.45	0.27	0.56	0.42	0.55	0.38
	weighted with RL2	0.53	0.63	0.46	0.29	0.57	0.44	0.56	0.40
	weighted with Xa	0.53	0.63	0.44	0.26	0.56	0.41	0.55	0.38
	weighted with Xb	0.53	0.64	0.45	0.27	0.57	0.42	0.56	0.39
	weighted with Xc	0.53	0.61	0.43	0.25	0.55	0.40	0.54	0.37
	weighted with Xd	0.54	0.63	0.45	0.27	0.56	0.42	0.55	0.38

		Quality criterion per sample							
		SP R ² *	EXT R ² *	RL1 R ² *	RL2 R ² **	Xa R ² *	Xb R ² **	Xc R ² *	Xd R ² **
Number of indicator species per sample	unweighted	0.60	0.82	0.62	0.47	0.76	0.65	0.72	0.59
	weighted with SP	0.60	0.82	0.65	0.51	0.78	0.68	0.74	0.62
	weighted with EXT	0.58	0.86	0.68	0.57	0.82	0.74	0.76	0.67
	weighted with RL1	0.55	0.83	0.73	0.61	0.84	0.76	0.79	0.70
	weighted with RL2	0.52	0.81	0.73	0.65	0.84	0.79	0.78	0.73
	weighted with Xa	0.56	0.84	0.71	0.59	0.83	0.75	0.78	0.69
	weighted with Xb	0.55	0.84	0.72	0.62	0.84	0.77	0.78	0.71
	weighted with Xc	0.58	0.83	0.70	0.58	0.82	0.73	0.77	0.68
	weighted with Xd	0.56	0.84	0.72	0.61	0.83	0.76	0.78	0.70

* calculated from linear regression.

** calculated from quadratic regression.

SP with the stricter criteria, the correlation coefficients decreased (Table 1). The combination of EXT and RL2 in the one-quality criteria (index Xb) reflected a firm link between species richness and species conservation. Therefore, we recommend the weighting factors in Table 2 that are based on Xb.

Fig. 3 illustrates the steps for improving the indicator species method using the old unweighted list, the unweighted expanded list and the weighted (Xb-derived) expanded list. The use of all 30310 vegetation surveys of the BBK database resulted in a scatterplot with many overlapping points and made the visualization of outliers and primary points impossible. Thus, the scatterplots in Fig. 3A–C were restricted to 800 randomly selected vegetation surveys from the database.

In assessing the improvement from step 1 to step 3, the biases in this type of compiled database with information from different investigators, different sampling seasons, different sampling years and different heterogeneities within the mapping units must be noted. Despite inevitable methodical heterogeneities in the database, the trend is clearly reflected in Fig. 3A–C as well as in Table 3A and B.

3.2. Checking threshold values of indicator taxa as eligibility criterion for remuneration

A critical point is the threshold for eligible grasslands. The common threshold value in Germany equals four indicator plant taxa per test area. As the expanded list contains many more indicator taxa than the old list, more plots may meet the threshold when the new list is used. The percentage of included plots in Fig. 4 serves as a calibration criterion to adjust the thresholds of different calculation methods. Fig. 4 shows that the threshold of 4 indicator taxa for the old checklist corresponds to approximately 5 indicator taxa for the new, weighted expanded checklist. The surprisingly small difference between the two corresponding threshold values can be explained as follows: (i) According to the new method, weak indicator taxa (mostly the very frequent indicator taxa) are down-weighted in the count whereas the indicator taxa using the old method are counted unweighted. (ii) The species added to the old list for developing the expanded list are predominantly rarer species that are relevant for nature conservation. The probability that many of these rarer species will occur together in the same area is rather low. However, the higher weighting of these 'hard' indicator taxa ensures that the joint occurrence of a few of these species already leads to a better rating class. Compared to the expanded list, the old checklist also indicates that an increasing threshold above 4 leads to more rapidly decreasing amount of plots that meet the indicator criterion. This result can be explained by the fact that highly species-diverse grasslands require a more differentiated checklist that encompasses a broader spectrum of 'hard' indicator species. The results underline the need for an expanded checklist if a multilevel payment on the basis of differentiated thresholds is intended. Notably, the plot assessment in Fig. 4 was only possible based on simple one-plot calculations due to data availability. Commonly, the indicator method used in some federal states of Germany is based on the assessment of 3 subtransects per plot, and each of the 3 subtransects has to meet the indicator criterion for remuneration. Therefore, with this indicator method, fewer plots would fulfill the remuneration criterion, as suggested by Fig. 4. However, it can be assumed that the relative differences between the different methods remain unchanged even when using a single-plot assessment. In addition, the different plot sizes contained in the database additionally influence species diversity as a result of species-area relationship (see Rosenzweig, 1995). As the number of indicator species and all the other quality criteria used are equally influenced by this factor, it can be assumed that the correlation between these variables remains nearly unaffected.

In Fig. 5, we apply the group thresholds of the HNV concept in Germany using the old indicator checklist of Brandenburg. The figure illustrates the group means with respect to index Xb. An index value of

Fig. 3. A-3C. Steps for improving prediction quality of the indicator species list.

1 denotes the average of the BBK database in terms of a combined value for EXT and RL2. The figure shows a well-marked increase in mean group Xb with an enhanced indicator taxa level as expected. However, the SDs reveal large amount of overlap among the groups, which would suggest the need for an improved multilevel method.

In comparison to the old checklist, the expanded checklist resulted in a larger spread of weighted and unweighted indicator numbers of the database. This result allowed broader group width and an increase to 5 groups of indicator numbers.

Based on Fig. 4 and using the suggested extended indicator method, the thresholds for a multilevel remuneration could be 5, 8, 11 and 14. An updated graphic that considers the new thresholds is presented in Fig. 6. The scattering within the groups was reduced by using the weighted indicator method. This process demonstrates the improvement in indicator power by weighting the indicator taxa. However, the SDs still exhibited overlap among the groups. This result could be expected and is partly attributed to the kind of data collection in the BBK

database (see earlier in the text). The database used did not allow an absolute suitability test of the indicator methods for a result-oriented stepwise remuneration. However, it was possible to show the relative increase in quality caused by the improved indicator method.

4. Discussion

The presented procedure shows the possibility of identifying suitable indicator species, determining their influence on the conservation quality criteria and establishing weighting factors for the indicator species. Since the number of indicator species is a subset of both species numbers (SP) and the number of species indicating extensive use (EXT), the correlation between the number of indicator species and the two criteria necessarily contains an autocorrelative proportion. From a statistical point of view, it is not surprising that an extension of the indicator list leads to a closer relationship between these two criteria (Table 3A and B), as the autocorrelative percentage increases. Since the

Fig. 4. Threshold values of the indicator taxa in relation to percentage of plots that contain at least the respective threshold number of indicator taxa (calculation from the BBK database).

Fig. 5. Indicator groups and their corresponding means and standard deviations (SDs) of index Xb using the old checklist for Brandenburg – thresholds are according to the rules of the HNV concept (Anonymous, 2017).

indicator species are also part of biodiversity, the autocorrelative component in the statistical analysis should not be eliminated.

Surprisingly, the different methods of species weighting scarcely improved the correlative relationship between indicator number and species number. Notably, SP is a general, nonspecific criterion and contains not only typical grassland species but also a series of species that are mainly distributed in other habitats (such as arable weeds or ruderal species). Some of these species can become invasive weeds and are undesired in grasslands. In contrast, EXT contains typical grassland species that are characteristic of extensive use (Matzdorf et al., 2008). These species are susceptible to impacts from intensification; they reflect the important component of floristic species diversity in grasslands. As a subset of EXT, RL2 represents the strictest conservation criterion. We argue that the proposed combination of EXT and RL2 within index Xb provides a balanced assessment criterion that summarizes different aspects of species diversity relevant to conservation in one value. The weighting of the indicator species improved the accuracy of the prediction determined based on the indicator species for both EXT and RL2 (see determination coefficients in Table 3A and B). We can therefore conclude that the predicted values of all established quality criteria benefited from the expansion of the indicator list. Moreover, the proposed weighting of the indicator taxa led to an

Fig. 6. In contrast to Fig. 5, indicator grouping is carried out on the basis of the new checklist using broader group widths.

upgraded in the more conservation-relevant habitats in the assessment procedure, an intended effect. The improvement in the predictive quality of the indicator list (see Fig. 3A–C) is crucial for a more precise allocation of grasslands to payment levels and thus for a more effective distribution of the remuneration.

The advanced indicator method leads to an expanded distribution of the indicator species numbers (Fig. 6). The resulting division into more than 4 groups enables a more differentiated remuneration of the most valuable areas in terms of conservation.

The comprehensive regional mapping data used have the advantage that they reflect the diversity of grassland habitats in a region well. However, this advantage is countered by the non-negligible confounder variables associated with such a data source (differences in the area size of the mapping units, variable recording intensities by different participants, different recording seasons, etc.). In particular, the first source of error could affect the validity of the results. Even if species saturation can be assumed as the mapping areas are mostly far above the minimum area, different mapping sizes lead to different spatial heterogeneities in species composition caused by different site heterogeneities (Davies et al., 2005; Öster, Cousins, & Eriksson, 2007). One could therefore assume that the variable factor 'size of the mapping area' dominates and misrepresents the results of the investigation to a large extent. Pearson's correlation coefficients of the size of the area to the quality criteria SP, EXT, RL1 and RL2 were 0.128, 0.013, 0.023 and 0.016, respectively. The correlations are very weak but significant at the 0.05 P-level due to high number of replicates, which indicates that the results presented were not unduly distorted by the variability in area sizes.

Most similar result-oriented indicator approaches in Europe are based on the prerequisite that farmers are able to monitor indicator species themselves. This approach requires that a checklist of easily identifiable species that is not too long is available (Briemle & Oppermann, 2003). The expanded list of indicators presented here also demonstrates a preference toward more easily identifiable species. Similar-looking species have also been summarized into species groups. However, farmers cannot reliably identify 71 indicator taxa quickly. In most cases, a botanist needs to be involved. The acceptance of the approach presented here could decrease as a result of the increased effort involved, both by farmers and by the responsible authorities, which would lead to higher transaction costs. However, this external monitoring could be combined with support for farmers or integrated as part of a joint inspection of the land. This approach could even lead to an improvement in acceptance of monitoring (Briemle & Oppermann, 2003). Transaction costs for such external monitoring combined with support should be included in the premiums for the measures. Further

studies on the issue of acceptance are necessary.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2019.125752>.

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